

Management innovation in Moroccan firms

Questionnaire for CEOs (or director generals or general managers)

Company Number: ...

SECTION I: Firm’s Management Innovation

1. Circle a number from 1 to 7, indicating your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements regarding management innovation practices within your firm:

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Rules and procedures within our organization are regularly renewed	1	2	3	4	5
We regularly make changes to our employees’ tasks and functions	1	2	3	4	5
Our organization regularly implements new management systems	1	2	3	4	5
The policy with regard to compensation has been changed in the last three years	1	2	3	4	5
The intra- and inter-departmental communication structure within our organization is regularly restructured	1	2	3	4	5
We continuously alter certain elements of the organizational structure	1	2	3	4	5

SECTION II: Firm Data

- 2. Industry where your firm is operating:
- 3. What is the age of your firm (in years)?
- 4. How many full-time employees are presently working for your firm?

5. Is your firm currently pursuing an innovation strategy?

Yes No

Questionnaire for the Head of Production Department

Company Number: ...

Circle a number from 1 to 7, indicating your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements regarding the leadership style of your firm’s CEO, director general or general manager (CEO for short):

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SECTION I: CEO’s Leadership

My CEO helps me understand how my objectives and goals relate to that of the company.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO helps me understand the importance of my work to the overall effectiveness of the company.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO helps me understand how my job fits into the bigger picture.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO makes many decisions together with me. .	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO often consults me on strategic decisions.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO solicits my opinion on decisions that may affect me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO believes that I can handle demanding tasks.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO believes in my ability to improve even when I make mistakes.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO expresses confidence in my ability to perform at a high level.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO allows me to do my job my way.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

My CEO makes it more efficient for me to do my job by keeping the rules and regulations simple.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My CEO allows me to make important decisions quickly to satisfy customer needs.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SECTION II: Demographics

1. What is your age?
2. For how long have you been working in this position?
3. What is your gender?

Female Male

SECTION II: Voicing Opinions & Concerns

Circle a number from 1 to 7, indicating your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements relating to the extent to which you voice your opinions and concerns:

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

I develop and make recommendations concerning issues that affect this work group	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I speak up and encourage others in this group to get involved in issues that affect the group	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I communicate my opinions about work issues to others in this group even if my opinion is different and others in the group disagree with me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I keep well informed about issues where my opinion might be useful to this work group.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I get involved in issues that affect the quality of work life here in this group.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I speak up in this group with ideas for new projects or changes in procedures.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SECTION III: Group Dynamics

Circle a number from 1 to 7, indicating your degree of agreement or disagreement with the following statements regarding your opinions and beliefs about groups at work:

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Group welfare is more important than individual rewards.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Group success is more important than individual success.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Being accepted by members of your work group is very important.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Employees should only pursue their goals after considering the welfare of the group.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Managers should encourage group loyalty even if individual goals suffer	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Individuals may be expected to give up their goals in order to benefit group success.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7